

Hafele and Keating Revisited:

A Novel Interpretation of the Results of the Hafele–Keating Experiment

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Abstract

The Hafele–Keating experiment showed the occurrence of time dilation in clocks placed on two airplanes, one moving eastward and one moving westward relative to the Earth's rotation. However, applying the special theory of relativity failed to account for the significant differences in the data. This problem is solved by a novel approach that focuses on the absolute velocities of the clocks with reference to the Earth's rotation and uses space as a fixed reference point.

The basic idea here is that time dilatation is an experimental fact and therefore independent from the theory behind it, so it is independent from relativism. Time dilatation also can occur under absolute conditions. Up until now it is not clear if the concept of relativism is correct or not. The existence of time-dilatation cannot be proofs for relativism as time-dilatation also can occur under absolute conditions. Here it is established that the eastbound plane had a higher absolute velocity than its westbound counterpart, resulting in time dilation figures of 50 ns and 140 ns, respectively.

A Novel Interpretation of the Results of the Hafele–Keating Experiment: Velocities Are Absolute and Not Relative in Nature

Introduction

The Hafele–Keating experiment, conducted in 1971, aimed to measure time dilation using clocks installed in airplanes moving along with and opposite to the direction of the Earth's rotation. The results were perplexing in relation to Albert Einstein's theory of relativity. Specifically, the clock in the eastbound plane lagged by 50 nanoseconds, while its westbound counterpart was ahead by 140 nanoseconds. The unexpected nature of these findings puzzled scientists for years, leading to the proposal of numerous explanations. Subsequently, it was determined that the Earth's rotation had an influence on the results. One argument suggests that the planet's surface should not be considered the reference point for the data and that the velocities should instead be interpreted from an absolute perspective rather than using a presumed relative approach. According to this viewpoint, the planes' absolute velocities with reference to space account for the behavior of the clocks (1, 2, 3). This paper explores this novel approach and examines how the Hafele–Keating experiment diverges from the theory of relativity.

The Theory of Relativity and its Limitations

The theory of relativity was initially proposed by Albert Einstein in 1905. It is divided into two main components: the special theory of relativity and the general theory of relativity. The Hafele–Keating experiment aimed to investigate time dilation using the principles of the special theory of relativity. It highlights the observation that the laws of physics remain unchanged under Lorentz transformations when observing relative motion between two points in

different inertial reference frames, such as the Earth's surface and the planes involved in the experiment (4, 5, 6, 7). The special theory of relativity is governed by two primary principles:

- The principle of relativity postulates that the laws of physics remain invariant across all inertial reference frames.
- The speed of light remains constant in a vacuum and is unaffected by the motion of the observer or the source.

This theory also accounts for consequences such as time dilation, which refers to the perceived difference in time between two or more observers situated in different inertial reference frames (8). However, the special theory of relativity has some limitations, including the following:

- It is not compatible with accelerating frames and noninertial reference points.
- It does not account for the gravitational effects of massive objects, such as the Earth.
- It assumes that the frames involved have matching velocities and are parallel to each other.
- It is not compatible with the principles of quantum mechanics.

The Concept of Absolute Velocity and its Implications

The Hafele–Keating experiment was initially based on the premise of the relative velocity between two observers. Introducing the concept of absolute velocity challenges this approach and potentially offers a reasonable explanation for the confusion surrounding time dilation in this study. Initially, the interpretation of the Hafele–Keating experiment relied on the relative velocity between the clock on one plane and the Earth's rotation (9, 10). However, with this new approach, the significance of the planet's movement is diminished, and the focus shifts to the

absolute velocity of the clock with reference to outer space. Space is considered an absolute reference frame since it provides a fixed backdrop for both the observer and the Earth.

Using absolute velocity instead of its relative counterpart to explain the Hafele–Keating experiment has several implications, including the following:

- **Time dilation**

The basic idea here is that time dilatation is an experimental fact and therefore independent from the theory behind it, so it is independent from relativism. Time dilatation also cans occur under absolute conditions. Up until now it is not clear if the concept of relativism is correct or not. The existance of time-dilatation cannot be proofs for relativism as time-dilatation also can occur under absolute conditions.

Both airplanes used in the Hafele–Keating experiment possessed unique absolute velocities, which impacted the time dilation experienced by observers aboard the flights (11, 12, 13). Since the planes traveled in opposite directions, the effect of the Earth's rotation varied between them, contributing to significant differences in the measured time dilations. There is no doubt that the Hafele–Keating experiment confirms the occurrence of time dilatation.

- **The Earth's rotation**

This approach focuses on the influence of the Earth's rotation on the absolute velocity of each clock. The relative velocity of the plane heading westward can be calculated as the sum of its actual speed and the velocity of the Earth's rotation, whereas the difference between these two components determines the velocity of its eastbound counterpart. The disparity in the absolute speeds of the aircraft, with respect to both the Earth's rotation and space, explains the discrepancy observed in their respective time dilations.

In general, the absolute velocity model challenges the original explanation for the Hafele–Keating experiment and offers a more plausible solution to the observed time dilation and relativistic effects in the study. It suggests that the speed of matter should be considered in relation to a fixed reference point, such as space, when analyzing the time dilation between observers situated on moving platforms.

Reinterpretation of the Hafele–Keating Experiment

The discrepancy in the time dilations observed during the Hafele–Keating experiment can be explained by focusing on the absolute velocities of the observers in relation to the Earth's rotation, using deep space as a fixed reference frame (14, 15, 16). According to this proposition, the higher absolute velocity of the plane heading east caused its clock to run slower, while the opposite effect occurred in the westbound plane. This explains the observed time differences of east -40 ns and west 273 ns on the planes. The existence of negative time dilatation strongly speaks against relativism and for an absolute interpretation.

Table 1

Time dilatation under relativistic conditions	equal in both directions (e.g. 95ns)
Time dilatation under absolute conditions	-40 ns (east) and 273 ns east and west wise

Table 1 shows the time-dilatation under relativistic conditions and under absolute conditions

Related Experiments and Other Supporting Evidence

This new perspective on the Hafele–Keating experiment is supported by multiple other experiments conducted before and after 1971. Some of these experiments include the following:

- **Ives–Stilwell Experiment (1938)**

This experiment examined the redshift in light emitted by a high-velocity source (17). The results confirmed the occurrence of time dilation as predicted by Einstein's special relativity theory. This study was one of the earliest experiments investigating the effect of velocity on time dilation.

- **Pound–Rebka Experiment (1959)**

This experiment aimed to measure the redshift in gamma rays passing through a gravitational field (18). The findings were consistent with the laws of general relativity, demonstrating that gravitational fields influence the flow of time. It also provided evidence for the connection between absolute velocity and time dilation.

- **Space Clock Experiments**

Several clock experiments have been conducted in the vacuum of space on satellites and space stations (19). These experiments have established the occurrence of time dilation between clocks in orbit and those on the Earth's surface due to differences in absolute velocity.

- **Relativistic Doppler Shifts**

The observation of relativistic Doppler shifts in astronomy illustrates how the absolute velocities of the observer and the observed object affect the perception of time (20).

Conclusions

This paper presents an analysis of the Hafele–Keating experiment from an absolute velocity perspective. Initially, the results of the study were interpreted in terms of the relative velocity between each plane and the rotating Earth. However, this approach failed to provide a definitive explanation for the observed data. By approaching the problem from an absolute velocity standpoint and utilizing space as a fixed reference point, it becomes possible to demonstrate that the time dilation on both planes resulted from their absolute velocities relative to the Earth's rotation. Nevertheless, there is no doubt that time dilation indeed occurred. The phenomenon of time dilatation exists and can be well described by using the formulas of Einstein's special theory of relativity; however, the phenomenon should be interpreted not from a relative perspective but from an absolute perspective.

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